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Intellectual Property Values: What Do Musicians Talk About When They Talk About Copyright?

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Abstract

Based on interviews with musicians who sit on the margins of the music industry and for whom music is not their main source of income, this paper reports on how these artists and performers think and talk about copyright. If, as many suppose, the business of making music is more and more about the distribution of rights, how are these rights understood and deployed in the practices of these musicians? What are these rights seen to protect and to what end? The paper explores these questions by considering how aspiring musicians think about 'music', about themselves as musicians, and about the relationship between copyright and wider social values. It reveals that their attitudes are often a mixture of the pragmatic and principled, where that pragmatism is not simply linked to money, any more than principle is solely about the musicians' claims as creators. Information can be more valuable than cash; loyalty to their fellow musicians more prized than the recognition of individual talent.

Introduction

Back in the 1960s, Frank Zappa and his group the Mothers of Invention parodied the Beatles' album, *Sgt Pepper's Lonely Hearts Club Band*. Imitating the iconic gatefold sleeve, Zappa entitled his satire *We're only in it for the money*. The Beatles had 'sold out' was the simple message. They should be making music for love or for art, not for cash. This crude

dichotomy was a common-place of musical criticism in those heady days, and while the basic choice that it implied was never a real one, it did assume that making money from music was a realistic (if ‘debased’) hope.

Today, such a choice hardly seems to exist. Making money from music is increasingly difficult. But making music remains a popular activity, and the desire to be a musician is still strong (one of our interviewees described it as a ‘compulsion’ [CT, interview, 28th August 2013]¹). The issue is how to realise such ambitions. Creativity has to be resourced. The issue is how this is to be done and under what conditions – from ‘free’ labour to a ‘portfolio’ of income streams (see Hesmondhalgh and Baker, 2011; Stahl, 2013; and Schlesinger and Waelde, 2012). In such a world, the motivations of musicians are already confused and complicated; they become more so with the emergence of new forms of creation, production and dissemination.

In these new conditions, both the definition of what it is to be a musician and what value lies in music become open to question. The music-making ‘business model’ is no longer organized around the exchange of objects. This is partly because music is increasingly seen as a ‘service’ (Fontaine-Skronski, 2014), and partly because what is valued is not hard cash, but other forms of exchange.

This new order is captured by the plaintive plea of the musician Zoe Keating: ‘I wish I could make this demand: stream my music, but in

¹ The initials of interviewees have been changed to protect their anonymity

exchange give me my listener data. But the law doesn't give me that power. The law only demands I be paid in money, which at this point in my career is not as valuable as information. I'd rather be paid in data.' (quoted in Tschmuck, 2013) For Keating, the issue is not about making music for love (or for free) versus making it for money. Her desire is for a different kind of currency: information.

The same thought is echoed by a musician that we interviewed. 'My attitude is like a start-up', he said, 'you build up a community and then you monetize it ... Give it away free, remove all the obstacles that would normally be there ... I never actually gave music away free, I would swap it for an email address.' (LT, interview, 6th August 2013) In the early stages of his career, he was not worried about fans getting his music without paying, as long as he got their email address in exchange. For him, email addresses were much more valuable than any income he might have lost.

What both these musicians seem to be doing is working against the business models and assumed incentives that have traditionally framed the music industry. They call into question the familiar relationship between copyright law and creativity (Gaines, 1991), and in so doing suggest that we should look again at how the language and terms of copyright operate within the creative process, particularly among those on the fringes of that business. We are not alone in this thought. Philip Schlesinger and Charlotte Waelde (2012: 25) make a similar point: 'Both the law and cultural policy tend to focus on the product of cultural work and how it can be protected and exploited. What receives much less attention is how creative milieu

actually operate and the value systems of those who work in them.’ One of the implications of this is that ‘copyright’ takes on a different guise too. In this paper, we explore how musicians who, in finding their way through the new digital economy, talk about copyright. In particular, we explore how they think about copyright and how this is connected to the way they think of themselves and their art and their creative practices.

Background

Like Schlesinger and Waelde, our concern is with practice rather than with formal legal principle. Our research examines the ways in which ‘copyright’ features in the working routines of musicians that sit on the ‘digital margins’; that is, those people who make music for public performance and distribution, who aspire to be professional musicians, but who are not able to rely on music as a source of income. Our questions are about how such musicians think about copyright and how it features in their creative practices. In particular, we are curious about how they conceive of ‘copyright’ and what it represents to them, and how their thinking coincides or deviates from conventional understandings of copyright and its rationale (see Stokes, 2003: 10-22). We ask these questions because we are curious about how the meanings copyright assumes differs from that which is assumed by legislators and regulators, or by those who typically speak about copyright on behalf of the music industry.

More particularly, we are interested in the political and ethical values that shape, and are constituted by, our respondents' views on copyright. Our research asks about how musicians on the margins think about music – whether they see it as a 'thing' to be owned or to be shared; how they distinguish recorded music from other forms and other products. Specifically, are attitudes to copyright simply a product of financial self-interest? Do musicians who do not depend on music for their income also not care about copyright? And if so, what is it that they do care about? Are there other values at work, ones that work against crudely instrumental self-interest? Schlesinger and Waelde (2012: 26) suggest that artists who sit on the fringes of the creative industries are engaged in creating a portfolio of work. While such artists may espouse a belief in the 'romantic' conception of creativity, they also have to negotiate the conflicting pulls of art and the need for financial security. These realities and dispositions do not make copyright redundant, but they do give it a context in which it represents one value or issue among the many with which musicians work. Do these views differ depending on whether they are talking about live performance or recordings, whether they are composers or 'just' musicians, whether they sample or not, whether they are in a band or are a solo artist, a jazz musician or a rock one? These are the questions that we explored.

Put simply, our concern is with the values and assumptions that inform musicians' views of copyright. How do they think of, and about, copyright – how does this thinking differ from legal and industry discourses? We present our findings under three headings: 1. The value (and nature) of

music; 2. Being a musician; 3. Copyright and citizenship. These represent the different dimensions to the talk about copyright that we recorded. The first concerns the value attributed to 'music' by our respondents. We wanted to know how they understood the entity which copyright was designed to protect – was it a form of property or an aspect of themselves? Could it be valued in monetary terms? Our second concern is related to this, but the focus is on them as musicians. What does it mean to be a musician? Is it a trade or an art? Is it about teamwork or individual contributions? And finally we wanted to know how attitudes to copyright might be informed by their wider set of social and political values, or does it exist as a narrowly defined legal concept only? These three elements constitute, we suggest, the key dimensions to understanding how copyright features in the culture of the musicians that we have studied.

Method and data

The data reported here was collected, first, through an online survey (n=162). This asked respondents to comment on their experience as a musician, the genre in which they worked, and their knowledge of copyright, among other issues. The results of this survey are reported in another paper (Phillips and Street, forthcoming). For this paper we have relied on the individual, semi-structured interviews with which we followed up the survey. In these (n=20) we asked a smaller sub-sample of our musicians, representing a variety of genres and a range of experience, about how they thought of their music and their musical practices, and

what role copyright played in them. These interviews were recorded, and the responses coded according to the three dimensions described above.

1. This thing called music

Copyright law, and the way it is discussed (particularly within legal scholarship), tends to construct music as an 'object'. More precisely, it is understood as a thing over which rights of ownership – intellectual property - provide the basis for reward.

Of course, this simple assertion admits to many subtleties and qualifications, not least because of IP's focus on music in its written form and on the limits afforded to performance rights (Stokes, 2009). To present music as a 'thing' is still to beg questions as to what exactly constitutes the object that is music, what elements of the sound are to be 'owned'. For example, IP law has, according to some writers, tended to construct music in a gendered and ethnocentric way (McLeod and DiCola, 2011). Matt Stahl (2013) has suggested that the copyright regime is a direct product of capitalism and the relations of production that it entails. Music thereby becomes an alienated product of wage labour. These criticisms highlight how law – or its application – can be seen to privilege particular features of the music's creation and reproduction. The law may, in other words, constitute music in different ways. And the fact that what is copyrighted is no simple matter underlies our questioning of musicians. What do they

understand 'music' to be? How far do musicians adopt the conventional, legal representation of music?

It will come as no surprise that the picture which emerges is not consistent or uniform. Some musicians were quick to say that their music was 'more important' than property (where the comparison was with personal possessions – cars, for example). It may also be more important than the instruments on which that music is played: 'It's [my music] more important than property ... It's more important than the guitars I have, or the house that I don't have. ... It's visceral, I guess' (BL, interview, 28th August 2013).

Others refused the basis of the comparison all together. Music is not a 'thing' at all. But in saying this musicians described downloading as theft, as the taking of property: 'I think downloading is illegal ... is stealing' (LH, interview, 12th October 2013). And another used the same language in respect of sampling: 'You are stealing it ... It's their work ... It's really difficult ... I don't really know what I think about it, because I do steal it' (EL, interview, 5th July 2013). So while musicians disavowed the idea of music as property, they used the associated language to establish their attitudes and relationship to it.

We also found musicians, sometimes those who tried to avoid the language of property, who were comfortable with the idea of music as something from which revenue could be derived (e.g. EL, interview, 5th July 2013). But in accepting music as an object to be traded in the market, further distinctions were drawn. At the general level, there was a

distinction to be made between two types of 'value': the cultural and the monetary.

Q: 'Do you think of music as property? As something you own? Or do you think of it [music] as part of yourself?

LI: 'Yes, absolutely ... I never see it as having monetary value. It has a lot of emotional value; it has a lot of cultural value in some respects. I want people to enjoy it and get something from it. ... It's only at the point now that I have to sell my music to people and to ask for money ... And when you start making money, that's the weirdest thing ...' (LI, interview, 2nd August 2013).

Here the musician is representing music as an extension of herself. It is this that gives it emotional and cultural value. But at the same time, as she acknowledges that she is in a position to be able to sell her music, she accepts that it is also a source of monetary value.

Monetary value resided in the physical objects in which music was captured. This might be CDs, for instance, but it could also take other forms too: music as something to be traded, as we noted at the beginning, for an email rather than cash (LT, 6th August 2013).

What is also involved in this line of questioning is the matter of the thing itself. What *is* the music exactly? When we pressed our musicians to say where exactly the 'thing-ness' was located, one of them told us that it existed in the melody - 'What is the song? I guess it's melody, isn't it, really?' (BL, 28th August 2013). He added that he might give a different answer if he

were the drummer. The thought here, in this aside, is that what is being valued, or sold, or protected depends on who you ask, on what aspect of the music they *make*.

Another dimension to what was meant by music was the state in which it existed – as a recording or as a performance. When the ‘object’ was a ‘performance’, we saw slightly different thought processes at work:

When you’re just playing live, it [copyright] was not something you thought about ... And also, I think, as a kind of solo performer with little experience of the music industry, I didn’t understand necessarily what it was. It was only as an adult, recording things, and having more contact with people from the industry, and maybe doing it yourself, it changes the whole thing ... you have to be aware of these things. ... The way that I value that [music] has changed. I still really don’t understand how it applies to myself. ... I can’t imagine anyone [copying my music]... I think it’s just a cluelessness. Also because our music isn’t heard enough ... More a presumption is that these songs are your own because they are your own. There’s no legality in that; they’re just yours. The more you grow up ... and the more that you learn about life, you realise that’s not enough ... It’s only been issue when it comes down to money ... the more costs you incur as a musician, you start to think about [copyright] (LI, 2nd August 2013).

These reflections, in which the musician is almost arguing with herself, is indicative of two important things that come out of this section. The first is that what music is – a thing or an aspect of identity, a melody or a rhythm, a

recording or a live performance – are all implicated in the discourses of copyright with which musicians work, however tenuously.

2. Being a musician

The idea that music might be a thing over which property rights can be claimed is itself linked to assumptions about what it means to be ‘a musician’. Put simply, we might expect a musician to think differently about music if they conceive of themselves as an ‘artist’ or as ‘craftsman/woman’ or as an ‘entrepreneur’. In interview, these differences emerged in various ways. One of our respondent suggested that they had little or no choice in the matter; it was more like illness:

Chris Rea ... said it’s not a gift, it’s a condition. I think there’s a strange compulsion that people have to make music ... the sense of wanting to express something to somebody ... I do it to keep my group going ... Like building a boat, looking after a vintage car’ (CT, interview, 28 August 2013).

For him, music was simply something he had to do. It was, to this extent, a selfish activity, or at least an individualistic one. Another musician told us: ‘I’m very unaware of my audience when I’m writing ... It’s just not the way I write.’ (LI, 2nd August 2013). Another of our interviewees echoed these sentiments: ‘I tend to do stuff that I like ... and then I’ll frame it. I’ll do things I’m interested in musically. ... If you don’t just do what you want to do, you’re in trouble’ (LT, interview, 6th August, 2013). Thinking and acting

like this creates a distinct relationship to music and the claims associated with it.

This can best be seen in the contrast between what we labelled the individualist musician and the one who looks to others. This latter category defined themselves in terms of their relationship with their audience. And what kind of musician they were was dependent on whether the audience represented a market to be exploited, or a community to be shared. The audience could serve either as a source of revenue or as a source of affirmation (BL, interview, 28th August 2013; LI, interview, 2nd August 2013). This latter role brought with it its own tensions. Affirmation might come in the repetition of the familiar – ‘audience favourites’; but this could mean that new songs were not always welcomed or enjoyed in the same way.

It became frustrating because there were songs that audiences really, really like ... There was a cover that we had to do, and some of the band thought that was a ‘cheap shot’, but I didn’t: if it was fun, it was fun (AE, interview, 20th August 2013).

In trying to strike a balance between what the performer and the audience wanted, the musician was negotiating their role as a supplier of a ‘service’ – to deliver the ‘old familiars’ – versus their sense of themselves as a creative artist. This was a theme of several interviews (eg KI, interview, 12th July 2013, and LT, interview, 6th August 2013). The constraining effects of the audience, and the mixed emotions that they generated, were tempered

when recording was involved. The audience was less able to exercise a conservative pull (LI, interview, 2nd July 2013).

These different identities as musicians, and the different relationships (or lack thereof) that they established, played into the ideas they had about the rights attaching to the music. For the individualists, there was little doubt: the music was theirs. But for those who derived their identity – albeit in part – through the audience, it mattered how that relationship was understood in order to appreciate how or whether it was ‘owned’, and indeed what sort of entity it was, and hence to what extent it might have legal significance.

This issue emerged more starkly in the alternatives represented by being an ‘amateur’ or ‘professional’ musician. It was the latter categorization, unsurprisingly, that was associated with an explicit, self-conscious awareness of, and concern about, copyright. There was a more subtle variant, or euphemism, for the distinction. This emerged in the idea of being a ‘serious’ musician. This is captured in the following statement, in which our interviewee echoes thoughts reported in the discussion of how music was understood: ‘Music has always been a business. We’re all very aware of that. We’re artists and we love our art, but music is a business and everything has to be done right. ... [For us] things have definitely become more business orientated with the prospect of a deal on the horizon’ (QP, interview, 31st August 2013). For this musician, an interest in the economic possibilities of music – having one’s craft become a viable income stream – establishes a sense of themselves as a “professional”. And this means that

things need to be 'done right'. One aspect of this is taking more of an interest in how copyright works. As he says: 'I work in this industry. I should have as much knowledge of the industry that I'm working [in as possible]. Thankfully the idea would be to build a team around you that really know what they're up to.' (QP, 31st August 2013)

Being 'serious' about music is not, though, just about making money, it is also about caring deeply (AE, interview, 20th August 2013; and LH, interview, 12th October 2013). This version of seriousness is memorably documented in Val Wilmer's (1992) *As Serious As Your Life*. When music is serious in this way, it does not automatically connect to copyright (LI, interview, 2nd August 2013). It entered because of a realization of the *value* of music (ibid.), where 'value' here refers to the way music matters to a musician's life as a creative artist. Asked to say what they meant by being a 'serious' musician, one of our respondents told us:

They're serious ... they're musicians ... they do it collaboratively ... By serious about it, I mean ... that their understanding of the machinations of all of it is more developed than certainly mine ... I think that they're awareness about ... they always speak in terms that I don't really get ... there's real potential for their band ... [another musician] is bit more of an 'artist' about it ... tries to protect what she is doing, but doesn't really understand ... (KI, interview, 12th July 2013).

'Seriousness' has other dimensions too. It has to do with belonging to a community of others:

When you start taking music seriously, you surround yourself with people ... and you move in circles and you talk about things, and all those things are so troubling. ... You have to know about these things... You couldn't get past a certain stage without knowing them ... We've gradually informed each other. (LH, interview, 12th October 2013)

Each of these comments reinforces the thought that how people think of themselves as *musicians* affects how they approach the politics of copyright. What is important, though, is that their identity as musicians is not marked simply by the amateur-professional distinction, and the degree to which music constitutes a source of income. It is also signalled by taking music 'seriously', something that may be marked by the time and energy devoted to it, or by its perceived artistic or creative value.

3. Copyright and citizenship

Musicians do not just live as creative artists. They live as citizens too; that is, their attitudes to copyright may be formed by experiences and values that derive from beyond the musical realm. We asked our musicians about their general views on copyright, and used their answers to detect appeals to wider political, social and moral values. So, for example, we heard one musician talk of the 'duty' that fans had to pay for the music of their favourite bands. 'I believe', she said, 'if you are a fan of music and you like of music then you have a duty, once you like that music, to buy that music' (LH, interview, 12th October 2013). Another referred admiringly to a

songwriter who shared writing credits with his entire band, even though their contribution was very modest compared to his own (CT, interview 28th August 2013).

Most of the musicians that we spoke to recognized copyright as a site in which money *and* morality were in play (see also AE, interview, 20th August 2013). The acceptability of sampling was qualified by the question of whether money was involved. If the track on which the sample appeared made money, then there was a need for copyright law to be observed. If no one was making money, then sampling without permission was deemed acceptable. Here is how one musician explained the problem:

I don't worry too much about people pinching our stuff ... but you know, if they use something on film or an advert, I'd be annoyed if we didn't get any money for it. It's too late to worry too much about [downloads]. I think that as long as you are credited for things ... and someone else isn't making money out of it, then I'm not too worried ... If they're making money, then I'd be more worried' (KI, interview, 12th July 2013)

Moral values also informed the way musicians thought about plagiarism. As one musician told us: 'I would find it very upsetting for example, if someone were to take an aspect of my song and call it their own, I would find it slightly reprehensible to do that to someone else.' (QP, interview, 31st August 2013) Such positions are, however, tempered by aesthetic considerations. The same musician noted that copyright protection can limit the creative process. But in acknowledging the tension, he sees it as a

moral dilemma: 'on a smaller scale, taking things and making it your own can be quite a cool thing. But it's a fine line, it's such a grey area; no one really knows what you're allowed to do.' (ibid.)

Another musician expressed a similar sense of unease and confusion over the issue of copying and/or claiming credit:

American folk music ... I imagine you can't copyright it ... arguments about arrangements being nicked ... There are songs that don't belong to anyone ... and I like those songs the best ... I can't understand why you would want someone to re-write your essay and say it was theirs ... That is about morality ... That's where the outrage is ... If they copied my music and it cost me money, that would make me livid (AE, interview, 20th August 2013)

And in contrast to these thoughts and the sentiments that they evoke, she also held to a more utopian vision: 'In terms of copyright ... my [attitude] is: isn't it just great that we can hear anything and that we can share' (ibid.). In giving voice to such a variety of views, she was not very different from most other musicians – or indeed, other citizens.

The tension between the law and everyday morality was played out in the experience of another musician. She described her band's decision to cover a song by a well-known US band and upload it to YouTube. Because it was made for 'aesthetic' reasons and because there were no plans to release her band's track, she felt justified in doing so without permission,

citing numerous other examples of song covers on YouTube in evidence (DR, interview, 27th September 2013). But because she was signed to a label at the time, she felt obliged to seek permission for the upload from the band, particularly as they were both on the same label. The US band endorsed the video via their official Twitter feed (ibid). Whether they did in fact have the power to grant this permission was unclear, but that was not the issue for her. The important question was what she felt were her obligations, given the absence of any financial game and the fact of a shared label.

Morality could trump the law. Whatever the law required, the issue was what was or was not disrespectful. As she said: 'If I saw that someone had released a cover of one of our songs I would hit the roof. If approval hadn't been given I would be really, really mad about it to be honest. ... It would be inconsiderate of someone not to get in contact' (ibid.). Her sense that it was inconsiderate, whatever the law, suggested that – for her – musicians belonged to a community in which certain moral codes should apply, irrespective of the law.

This sense of community, and its implications for a moral order, shaped thoughts around composition credits, about whose 'property' a piece of music was (AE, interview, 20th August 2013). This did not mean that musicians were all egalitarians, although some were: 'I think it's important to be a collective, and to be equal' (LI, interview, 2nd August 2013; see also MI, interview, 12th July 2013). Sometimes this egalitarianism was more pragmatic than principled. Sharing credit, even if this was not a

reflection of the distribution of effort or imagination, was done in the name of 'solidarity' (CT, 28th August 2013). The pragmatism was a reflection of life on the digital margins. Dividing rewards equally made sense:

... given the challenges that a band faces these days, literally any income that comes in has to go all the way around, it's just the only way to do it really. It used to be that the principal songwriter would maybe end up driving a Ferrari or buying a yacht ... but these days ... it's on a much smaller scale, so anything that comes in, we all deserve to have a part in it.' (LD, interview, 6th September 2013)

Others took a Lockean approach to intellectual property within the band. A musician who advocated a 'band agreement' – that established who contributed what – did so because of the need to distribute credit where credit was due. In this case, to the songwriter: 'It's such a personal thing. You write a song. "That's my song"; or 'we get protective over our parts ... Well, that song wouldn't be as good without my guitar part ...' (BL, interview, 28th August 2013). This tension between the personal and the communal is sometimes resolved through the drawing of borders that demarcate those inside and those outside the community.

Our musicians also made quite clear or sharp distinctions between band members who were within the communal circle and those who were outside, either because they played only occasionally or had recently joined (LI, 2nd August 2013). The different attitudes are well captured in this response:

We would always divide up writing royalties. It's a symbolic thing, as much as a practical thing. [Despite one person driving it all] ... You're all in this together ... It gave you a sense of cohesion. It was a very powerful incentive to hang together. Your stake in the project was equal to everyone else's. Recently, you've become a bit more aware of the financial implications, and all the other things that go with it, and it is important. It only becomes important when you start earning something from it. And in that way, I've been relatively untroubled by too many life or death issues. I've often thought ... there's a lot more to writing a song than I do, and yet at the end of the day I claim authorship ... I get everything together, I make it happen ... There was a period when we had five drummers in three months ...' (CT, interview, 28th August 2013)

But while musicians adopted different radically in the stances they took on writing credits, they shared the view that intention was to create 'fairness'. They differed in what they understood fairness to require. There was a clear sense that musicians deserved to be rewarded for the effort they expended - 'All [musicians] should be protected [including drummers] ... If you put the time in ...' (LH, interview, 12th July 2013), but this too came with qualifications. While it might be that session musicians contribute significantly to the music for which they are hired, it does not follow that they should receive a share of the royalties. They agreed, after all, to the terms of the session: 'Ethically, that's not necessarily right, but they agreed to it. It paid their bills; they knew what they were doing ...' (LT,

interview 6th August 2013). A similar attitude was reflected in an interviewee who complained about working as a session musician for a jingle composition for a television pilot, for which 'nobody was getting paid' (DG, interview, 4th September 2013).

In summary, we see attitudes to 'fairness' and other issues as informing attitudes to copyright. Not surprisingly, the values which musicians hold as citizens inform their views on copyright, hence the variations in those views. Copyright is a matter of politics as well as economics, and musicians are citizens as well as artists.

Negotiating the copyright maze

There is another sense in which musicians are like citizens. They operate within a knowledge economy and may lack or be denied the resources needed to access and act upon information. Our musicians were, by their own admission, often uncertain about the law on copyright, on what – in fact – they were allowed or not allowed to do.

One musician spoke of how, following Metallica's run-in with Napster, he resorted to what he – mistakenly – thought of as the 'poor man's copyright': the idea that sending a copy of your music to yourself establishes legal rights to it (IS, interview, 5th July 2013). Another confessed the limits to his own knowledge: 'I know the lengths of copyright. ... Apart from that I don't really know a huge amount' (QP, interview, 31st August 2013).

Few of the musicians we spoke to claimed any very detailed knowledge of copyright. Almost none had studied the topic. Most acquired their understanding in piecemeal fashion, as and when the occasion arose. They learnt from fellow musicians, or from managers or other figures within the industry. It is important to bear this in mind as we reflect upon the topic of this paper: what musicians talk about when they talk about copyright. They rarely talk about the law, or at least they rarely talk about the law as either a lawyer or a policy-maker would.

What we may conclude is that music is understood as 'property' and as other than property. Much turns on how musicians think of themselves, and about what aspect of their music-making lives that they are considering. They have many different relationships to copyright. And these relationships are mediated by other ones – their relationship to a profession, to band members, to their audience, and to a wider society (as citizens). They attribute different values to music and to copyright, depending on what relationship is being considered and how it is viewed. Copyright and the issues it raises vary with context and with musician. It is shaped by practical and political considerations.

For the musicians that we spoke to, copyright is constructed in the practices of musicians, and in the talk that constitutes it in the lives of musicians. It does not so much impose itself on the working lives of these musicians as become the object of negotiation and discussion. It represents a means – one of many – by which musicians understand themselves as artists (as 'serious') and as citizens. Their attitudes are often a mixture of

the pragmatic and principled, but that pragmatism is not simply associated with a desire for financial reward, any more than principle is derived solely from their claims as creators. Information can be more valuable than cash; loyalty to their fellow musicians more prized than the recognition of individual talent.

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